

Resilient and environmental friendly offshore wind farm projects

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Abstract—Offshore wind decommissioning in Germany is legally anchored decades before execution. However, the technological, ecological, and industrial conditions under which dismantling will occur remain inherently uncertain. German offshore regulations institutionalize uncertainty through performance-based standards, financial security, and a state-of-the-art clause. This paper examines German offshore regulations concerning decommissioning analyzing exemplarily the permit framework of Nordlicht I and the emerging decommissioning process of alpha ventus. The analysis shows that while attempts are made to integrate end-of-life considerations into the approval phase of offshore wind farms, the empirical data and standards required to operationalize these considerations are still lacking.

Index Terms—Resilience, environment, nature restoration, offshore wind farms, decommissioning

I. INTRODUCTION

Growing concerns about climate change [1] have accelerated the innovation, development, and deployment of renewable energy technologies around the world [2], [3]. Governments are increasingly seeking to secure national energy supply while simultaneously reducing greenhouse gas emissions. International frameworks such as the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), the Paris Agreement, and the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) provide clear guidance in this regard. In this context, offshore wind plays a strategic role in European electricity generation.

Thus, offshore wind has matured into a critical energy infrastructure in Europe in recent years. However, its regulatory architecture was built around construction and operation. Decommissioning entered the framework later, yet now it defines the credibility of long-term maritime governance.

According to § 58 of the German Offshore Wind Energy Act (WindSeeG), operators are required to remove installations after the end of their operating period and provide financial security before construction begins [4]. The site development plan 2025 and the associated environmental reports for the North Sea and Baltic Sea reinforce this obligation, particularly through the planning principle 6.1.5 [5]. The legal structure is clear: life-cycle responsibility is mandatory, not optional. What is less clear is how the dismantling will be performed in practice twenty-five years after the permit.

The life-cycle of an offshore wind farm typically consists of the phases of planning and permitting, design and construction,

operation and maintenance, and the end of life. Across the entire life-cycle, environmental protection duties are defined. In the planning and permitting phase, environmental impact assessments (EIA) and species protection assessments are required addressing birds, marine mammals, benthos, and protected areas [6]. In addition, ecosystem-based spatial planning, cumulative impact assessment, EU-wide cooperation, and continuous monitoring must be implemented [7]. Financial securities and guaranties are required before construction to ensure decommissioning and restoration even in insolvency [8]. In the construction phase, noise mitigation, such as bubble curtains to protect porpoises, the respect of seasonal construction windows, and habitat minimization, are common measures to protect the marine ecosystem [9].

Fig. 1. Depiction of the life-cycle of an offshore wind farm project.

In the operation phase, avoiding bird and bat collisions is crucial. Common measures are continuous monitoring, noise curtailment, and dimming concepts [9].

Finally, decommissioning defines removal obligations and restoration requirements. It needs to be decided on the following end-of-life options: (1) extension, (2) re-powering, or (3) complete removal [10], where the foundations might be left in place considering the artificial reef potential [8], [11], [12].

Foundation removal is at the core of the decommissioning debate as offshore wind structures alter seabed conditions. Research conducted in the context of alpha ventus and related offshore wind projects documents the effects of artificial-reefs and colonization of hard substrates by benthic communities [13]. What started as industrial infrastructure has become habitat. Full extraction restores the morphology of the seabed, but increases sediment disturbance. Partial removal reduces the intensity of the intervention, but leaves subsurface structures embedded in the sediment.

Evidence from the oil and gas sector shows that offshore structures function as artificial reefs that enhance local biodiversity and ecosystem connectivity, particularly in soft-bottom environments. However, these systems represent new ecosystems and there is still limited evidence on the long-term outcomes of different decommissioning strategies, while full removal may even conflict with conservation objectives. Consequently, recent research emphasizes the need for evidence-based case-by-case decisions rather than uniform removal policies [14].

Life-cycle assessment studies provide detailed information on material flows and embodied impacts [15]. These data are indispensable for evaluating the recycling potential in end-of-life options. Manufacturers have advanced recyclable blade technologies and circular material strategies. However, large-scale offshore implementation remains evolving. Decommissioning is therefore not solely a maritime safety issue. It is a material governance problem. Effective governance requires:

- contractual end-of-life provisions,
- transparency in material composition,
- verifiable recycling pathways,
- alignment between industrial capability and regulatory expectation.

This shows that uncertainty is managed institutionally, not technically.

II. TRADE-OFF BETWEEN NATURE AND RESILIENCE

Uncertainty arises not only from the time that passes from planning to decommissioning of an offshore wind farm, but also from the trade-off between safe operation and environmental protection. Offshore wind farms face tensions between reliable energy supply, safety and security, including defense, energy transition, and ecological protection [16]. The increasing integration of surveillance, sensors, and early-warning systems can introduce noise, traffic, and ecological disturbance [17]. The increasing risk of sabotage of sub-sea cables and infrastructure increases security demands [18], [19]. Environmental protection requirements in sensitive areas such as the Wadden Sea have led to offshore wind export cables being concentrated in a few shared corridors (e.g. via Norderney) to

minimize ecological disturbance. This bundling reduces spatial flexibility for grid planning and can increase infrastructure concentration, potentially creating trade-offs with system resilience and redundancy.

The critical infrastructures framework (KRITIS) implements the EU Critical Entities Resilience (CER) directive. In addition, it introduces unified national requirements concerning security, reporting, and crisis management controlled by the German Federal Office of Civil Protection and Disaster Assistance (Budesamt für Bevölkerungsschutz und Katastrophenhilfe, BBK) and the German Federal Office of Information Security (Budesamt für Sicherheit in der Informationstechnik, BSI) [20], [21].

Specifically, offshore-wind is collaboratively coordinated by the German Federal Network Agency (Bundesnetzagentur, BNetzA) and the German Federal Maritime and Hydrographic Agency (Budesamt für Seeschifffahrt und Hydrographie, BSH) to avoid duplicate regulation [22], [23]. This includes measures to prevent collisions between vessels and offshore wind farms, the establishment and monitoring of safety and exclusion zones, and the management of maritime traffic through navigational marking, as well as radar and AIS surveillance. KRITIS includes an all-hazard approach and identification of critical key infrastructure [24], [20] as well as cable security [25].

The following strategies are needed to integrate security, resilience, and environmental protection into offshore wind projects. Authorities must coordinate and use unified checklists, as well as recognize existing certifications. Security concepts should follow ecological design employing the following:

- Acoustically reduced detection, adaptive sonar, and lighting control.
- Risk-based planning: joint assessment of security, operational, and ecological risks.
- Shared monitoring systems that combine ecological and security sensors.
- Linking procurement requirements with environmental conditions.
- Planning early decommissioning, including removal of safety infrastructure and assessment of the reef.

III. EXAMPLE PROJECTS

In the following, we briefly analyze the regulatory framework of two offshore-wind farm projects, namely Nordlicht I (planning and construction phase) and alpha ventus (decommissioning phase).

A. Example 1: Nordlicht I

The Nordlicht I offshore wind farm is currently in the planning phase. The approval was given end of 2024, the final investment was secured in 2025 and in 2026 the construction is planned to start. The administrative plan approval decision for Nordlicht I specifies a dismantling sequence: rotor blades, nacelle, tower segments, internal cabling, scour protection and foundations [26]. Monopiles are to be cut below seabed level.

The cutting depth must ensure that there is no hazard to shipping or fishing, even with future sediment relocation [26].

The governance logic is defined in two clauses: First, the dismantling must comply with *generally recognized international standards*. Second, it must follow the *state of the art at the time of decommissioning* [26]. This combination is decisive, which means that compliance is judged both against internationally recognized standards and against the current state of the art. The permit defines performance objectives, hazard prevention, environmental protection, and removal obligation, but does not prescribe a specific engineering method. A detailed dismantling concept is required only in the planning phase and must be submitted before construction begins [26].

The framework is rigid in responsibility and flexible in technique. At the time of permit application, contractors are not selected, turbine models may change, recycling technologies evolve, and ecological knowledge remains incomplete. Thus, the regulation recognizes the uncertainty that is associated with decommissioning.

The Nordlicht I permit focuses on navigational safety rather than ecological baseline restoration [26]. The law defines hazard thresholds, not ecological end-states. This gap is not accidental. It reflects the absence of a normative consensus if decommissioning should re-establish pre-construction conditions, or acknowledge transformed ecosystems as a new environmental equilibrium.

B. Example 2: *alpha ventus*

Alpha ventus was the first offshore wind farm in the world to be commissioned in high-sea conditions and provided a research environment with 12 wind turbines. It was commissioned in 2010 as Germany's first offshore wind farm and is now approaching decommissioning. The operating entity (Deutsche Offshore-Testfeld und Infrastruktur GmbH & Co. KG, DOTI) has confirmed that a dismantling concept is being developed in coordination with BSH [27].

Public tender documentation indicates separate scopes for turbine dismantling, i.e., the wind turbine generator (WTG) scope and the Balance-of-Plant (BoP) structures scope, including foundations and cables [28]. Importantly, the scope of the BoP contemplates alternative technical options for foundation treatment, including partial pile removal and full extraction [28]. Re-powering was examined, but was considered impracticable due to structural and spatial constraints relative to the dimensions of modern turbines [27]. This illustrates another dimension of uncertainty: infrastructure designed under one technological paradigm may not accommodate the next.

IV. SUMMARY AND OUTLOOK

Germany has established the following regulations to ensure an environmentally friendly decommissioning. A binding removal obligation is in place (see § 58(1) Windenergie-auf-See-Gesetz, WindSeeG), which is a statutory obligation to remove offshore installations after the end of operation [4]. Financial security mechanisms are provided (see § 58(2) WindSeeG),

which describes the requirement to provide security for decommissioning costs prior to construction. Performance-based safety standards are provided to support the requirement that dismantling must prevent future hazards to shipping and fisheries, including potential sediment relocation [26]. Finally, a state-of-the-art clause is provided that enables technological evolution [26].

However, there are several unresolved issues. The ecological value of artificial reef structures must be acknowledged and more research is needed on the ecological impact of removing or keeping foundations. Therefore, standardized criteria are needed for partial versus full foundation removal. Empirical data from completed German offshore decommissioning projects are missing, as recently the first offshore-wind farms reached their end-of-life. Long-term circular economy metrics need to be integrated into permit regimes. Decommissioning in Germany is therefore not a finalized governance regime, but rather an adaptive governance framework operating under conditions of structured uncertainty.

Adaptive regulatory capacity in this context does not mean risk elimination, but the ability of institutions to manage evolving risks while maintaining accountability. Integrating empirical experience from offshore and onshore wind decommissioning can improve offshore regulatory design and reduce avoidable uncertainty where such transfer is appropriate.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The spelling and grammar of this manuscript was checked by Copilot. The authors thank the reviewers for the constructive feedback that helped improve this manuscript.

REFERENCES

- [1] UNFCCC, "Adoption of the Paris Agreement". Report of the Conference of the Parties on its twenty-first session, held in Paris from 30 November to 13 December 2015. 1/CP.21. 2016.
- [2] IRENA, "Future of wind: Deployment, investment, technology, grid integration and socio-economic aspects", A Global Energy Transformation paper. 2019.
- [3] IEA, "World Energy Outlook 2021", Paris, France. 2021.
- [4] Bundesamt für Justiz, Windenergie-auf-See-Gesetz (WindSeeG), § 58 Abs. 1–2, https://www.gesetze-im-internet.de/windsee_g/_58.html, accessed March 2026.
- [5] Bundesamt für Seeschifffahrt und Hydrographie, Flächenentwicklungsplan 2023 (Planungsgrundsatz 6.1.5) – BSH, https://www.bsh.de/DE/THEMEN/Offshore/Meeresfachplanung/Flaechenentwicklungsplan_2025/flaechenentwicklungsplan_2025_node.html, accessed March 2026.
- [6] BUND. "Offshore-Windenergie: Klimaschutz nur mit Meeresnaturschutz" Online: <https://www.bund.net/energiewende/erneuerbare-energien/windenergie/offshore-windenergie/>, accessed 2026.
- [7] OCEAN, Offshore Coalition for Energy and Nature. "Sechs Anforderungen für den naturverträglichen Ausbau von Offshore-Windenergie." Online: https://offshore-coalition.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/09/sechs-anforderungen-fur-den-naturvertraglichen-ausbau-von-offshore-windenergie_ocean_german-wg.pdf, 2024.
- [8] Deutscher Bundestag, Wissenschaftliche Dienste WD-8. "Rechtsrahmen für Offshore-Windenergie." Online: <https://www.bundestag.de/resource/blob/676100/88fa78f26a501e16a3ac18f64aa94d4a/WD-8-108-19-pdf.pdf>, 2019.
- [9] NABU. "Offshore-Windparks und Meeresnaturschutz." Online: <https://www.nabu.de/natur-und-landschaft/meere/offshore-windparks/index.html>, 2025.

- [10] C. Köpke, J. Mielniczek, and A. Stolz. "Testing resilience aspects of operation options for offshore wind farms beyond the end-of-life." *Energies* 16.12 (2023): 4771.
- [11] BMWK. "Offshore-Windenergie: Ein Überblick über die Aktivitäten in Deutschland." Online: <https://www.bundeswirtschaftsministerium.de/Redaktion/DE/Publikationen/Energie/offshore-windenergie.pdf>, 2015.
- [12] Stiftung Offshore-Windenergie. "Conditions for Sustainable Decommissioning of Offshore Wind Turbines." Online: https://www.offshore-stiftung.de/de/decommissioning_conditions_for_sustainable_decommissioning_of_offshore_wind_turbines, 2024.
- [13] J. Dannheim et al. "Benthic effects of offshore renewables: identification of knowledge gaps and urgently needed research," *ICES Journal of Marine Science*, 77(3), 1092–1108. doi:10.1093/icesjms/fsz018, 2020.
- [14] A M Fowler, A -M Jørgensen, J W P Coolen, D O B Jones, J C Svendsen, R Brabant, B Rumes, S Degraer, The ecology of infrastructure decommissioning in the North Sea: what we need to know and how to achieve it, *ICES Journal of Marine Science*, Volume 77, Issue 3, May-June 2020, Pages 1109–1126, <https://doi.org/10.1093/icesjms/fsz143s>
- [15] A. Arvesen et al. "Life cycle assessment of an offshore grid interconnecting wind farms and customers across the North Sea," *Int J Life Cycle Assess*, 19:826–837, DOI 10.1007/s11367-014-0709-2, 2014.
- [16] R. Mautz "Konflikte um die Offshore-Windkraftnutzung—eine neue Konstellation der gesellschaftlichen Auseinandersetzung um Ökologie." *Umwelt-und Technikkonflikte*. Wiesbaden: VS Verlag für Sozialwissenschaften, 181-197. https://link.springer.com/content/pdf/10.1007/978-3-531-92354-3_9, 2010.
- [17] M. Brake, Center for Advanced Security, Strategic and Integration Studies, CASSIS (Universität Bonn). "Mit Windkraft gegen Sabotage – neue Schutzmaßnahmen in der Ostsee." Online: <https://www.cassis.uni-bonn.de/de/medienbeitraege/mit-windkraft-gegen-sabotage-dr-moritz-brake-ueber-neue-schutzmassnahmen-in-der-ostsee>, 2025.
- [18] L. Stock and M. Krefting, WELT. "Die beträchtlichen Sabotage-Risiken für die Windparks vor der Küste." Online: <https://www.welt.de/wissenschaft/article254950852/Energie-Die-betraechtlichen-Sabotage-Risiken-fuer-die-Windparks-vor-der-Kueste.html>, 2024.
- [19] C. Köpke et al. "Resilience management processes in the offshore wind industry: schematization and application to an export-cable attack." *Environment Systems and Decisions* 43.2 (2023): 161-177.
- [20] BMI. "Pressemitteilung: Kabinettsbeschluss KRITIS-Dachgesetz." Online: <https://www.bmi.bund.de/SharedDocs/pressemitteilungen/DE/2025/09/kritis-dg-kabinett.html>, 2025.
- [21] OpenKRITIS. "KRITIS-Dachgesetz" Online: <https://www.openkritis.de/it-sicherheitsgesetz/kritis-dachgesetz-sicherheitsgesetz-3-0.html>, 2026.
- [22] BWO. "Stellungnahme zum KRITIS-Dachgesetz." Online: https://bwo-offshorewind.de/wp-content/uploads/2025/10/250904_BWO-Stellungnahme-KRITIS-Dachgesetz.pdf, 2025.
- [23] BWE. "Stellungnahme KRITIS-Dachgesetz." Online: https://www.wind-energie.de/fileadmin/redaktion/dokumente/publikationen-oeffentlich/themen/04-politische-arbeit/06-europa/20250904_BWE_Stellungnahme__Kritis_DACH_Gesetz.pdf, 2025.
- [24] Deutscher Bundestag. "Regierungsentwurf KRITIS-Dachgesetz." Online: https://www.kritisschutz.de/content/files/2025/11/RegE_Kritis-DachG.pdf, 2025.
- [25] F. Gehringer and M. Hesse "Lifelines under Threat - How We Can Make Europe's Maritime Critical Infrastructure More Resilient", Konrad Adenauer Stiftung, https://www.kas.de/documents/259121/35709985/EN_ai_01_25_Gehringer_Hesse.pdf/b7eb7541-43f2-0257-1e43-8e56f8c4bfab?version=1.0&t=1744367712377, 2025.
- [26] Bundesamt für Seeschifffahrt und Hydrographie, Planfeststellungsbeschluss Nordlicht I, Kapitel 5.3.3 Rückbau – BSH, <https://wp.bsh.de/blog/2025/01/17/bsh-macht-planfeststellungsbeschluss-fuer-den-offshore-windpark-nordlicht-i-ehemals-owp-n-7-2-oeffentlich-bekannt/>, accessed 2026.
- [27] alpha ventus – Pressemitteilung zum Rückbaukonzept, <https://www.alpha-ventus.de/presse/detail/das-testfeld-alpha-ventus-hat-seinen-zweck-erfolgreich-erfuellt-konzept-zum-umweltvertraglichen-rueckbau-wird-erarbeitet>, accessed 2026.
- [28] TED (Tenders Electronic Daily) – EU-Vergabeportal, <https://ted.europa.eu> (Search: 'Alpha Ventus Decommissioning'), accessed 2026.